

REACTIVE HOT COMPACTION AND "IN-SITU" REINFORCEMENT COATING FOR INTERMETALLIC MATRIX COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a unique coupling of the reactive hot compaction (RHC) of intermetallics, such as Nb and Ni aluminides, with the in-situ formation of diffusion barrier coatings on refractory metal filaments used as reinforcements. The processing involves blending the elemental powders with pre-oxidized refractory metal filaments and reactively synthesizing the mixture at elevated temperatures. During RHC, the treated surfaces of the filaments react with the liquid aluminum to form in-situ a surface coating of alumina. Reaction sequences in the composites indicated that the initial alumina coating forms prior to the synthesis of the matrix in niobium aluminides and concurrent with the formation of the matrix in nickel aluminides. Microstructures of the composites in the as-processed and post-annealed conditions revealed that the coating was chemically stable during long-term annealing and minimized further matrix/reinforcement reactions, while uncoated reinforcements showed extensive degradation in both the as-processed and annealed conditions. The various toughening mechanisms will be discussed with special emphasis on the role of interfacial alumina layer for effective load transfer via partial interfacial decohesion.

1. Introduction

Future designs of advanced turbine engines indicate a requirement for the development of new materials which will be capable of operating at service temperatures significantly greater than the current maximum potential of Ni- and Co-based superalloys. Concurrently, reduced specific density is desired to compensate for increased centrifugal stresses on rotating parts, and improve the thrust to mass ratio for better payload and fuel efficiencies. Finally, improved corrosion resistance in an increasingly severe environment is sought.

Intermetallics and Intermetallic compound-based alloys are regarded as probable candidate materials to meet these requirements^{1,2}. A large number of recent studies has been undertaken in an attempt to more fully understand the processing-microstructure-properties relationships in these alloys to exploit the desirable combination of high melting point, low density and adequate environmental resistance³⁻⁷. However, a major obstacle in their utilization is that ordered intermetallics generally have little low-temperature tensile ductility and thus have very limited damage tolerance⁸.

Reinforcing such brittle intermetallics by compositing with a ductile fiber or filament is seen as one promising solution to this significant limitation^{3,9}. However, artificial composites in general contain reinforcements in contact with the matrix in a thermodynamically non-equilibrium state. As a result, the elevated temperature exposure during processing and in service is commonly accompanied by extensive reinforcement-matrix interaction. The extent of this interaction increases with time and temperature of exposure. The interactions may result in the formation of other brittle intermetallics, significant interdiffusion or altered interfacial geometry, all of which may cause undesirable modifications of the fracture mechanics of the

composite^{9,11,13}. Thus a stable matrix-reinforcement interface is critical to the long term stability of the composite. Since thermodynamic instability of artificial composites is generally expected, kinetic control is usually sought through the incorporation of a diffusion barrier at the interface.

As detailed below, both matrix materials in the present study exhibited extensive reactions with the ductile reinforcement, necessitating the utilization of an interfacial diffusion barrier coating. An effective diffusion barrier coating must be stable with respect to both the matrix and the reinforcement, plus it must eliminate the interdiffusion of matrix and reinforcement atoms across the interface. Among several choices for coating materials, alumina (Al₂O₃) is known for its microstructural stability, chemical compatibility with aluminides and low diffusivity at high temperatures and was chosen for incorporation into this study.

Reactive Hot Compaction (RHC) is a term used to describe a number of powder metallurgical densification processes characterized by the utilization of a chemical reaction between two or more starting species to form the final phases present in the microstructure. The present study utilizes elemental Al, Ni and Nb powders as the starting species. The processing consists of mixing the powders in the ratio required for the stoichiometric intermetallic and heating to initiate the intermetallic-forming reaction while applying pressure to the mixture to aid in densification.

Reactive powder processing eliminates the necessity of producing expensive pre-alloyed powders and generally aids densification and lowers the required amount of externally supplied heat as a result of the (usually large) enthalpies of formation of intermetallics from the elemental constituents.

The current study describes the successful application of RHC to form intermetallic matrix composites with fully dense matrices and simultaneously forming, in-situ, diffusion barrier interfacial coatings on pretreated, ductile, refractory metal reinforcements in two substantially different intermetallic systems. Table I summarizes some of the important physical properties of these intermetallics, β -NiAl and NbAl₃.

Table I. Comparison of the Physical Properties of NbAl₃ and NiAl		
	NbAl ₃	NiAl
Solid Solubility Range	≈ 0	15%
Crystal Structure	DO ₂₂	B2
Melting Temperature (°C)	1680	1638
Density (g/cm ³)	4.55	5.85
ΔH _f (kJ/mole)	-119	-72
Thermal Expansion Coefficient, α (ppm/°C)	11.2	15.1
Oxidation Constant, k _p (gm ² /cm ⁴ s)	3x10 ⁻¹⁰ (1000°C)	10 ⁻¹³ (1000°C)
		10 ⁻¹¹ (1300°C)
Polycrystalline K _{IC} (MPa√m)	2.5	5 - 6

2. Experimental

Producing the composites consisted of an oxidation pretreatment of the niobium filaments coupled with separately developed reactive synthesis processing scheme, modified (for each intermetallic) to reflect the different sequences of events during fabrication, as described below.

Elemental Al and Nb or Ni powders, in a ratio to produce stoichiometric NbAl₃ and NiAl, respectively, were mixed with the pretreated Nb filaments. The average niobium and aluminum powder diameters were 45 μm and 20 μm, respectively, for NbAl₃; and ranged from 3.6 μm to 11.5 μm (Al) and 3.0 μm to 45 μm (Ni) for NiAl. The powder mixture was cold compacted in a disk 38 mm diameter by 8 mm thick at a pressure of 10 ksi, followed by vacuum hot pressing in a boron nitride-lined graphite die. The hot press schedule is shown in Figures 2.1 and 2.2 for NbAl₃ and NiAl, respectively. The elemental powders were diluted with up to 30 percent pre-reacted NiAl for the latter matrix to facilitate densification (detailed below). Cold pressing of the green compact for NiAl was determined to be undesirable since some deformation of the niobium filaments occurred at this stage. For this matrix, the mixture was compacted using a mild vibratory cycle in the graphite die prior to hot pressing to increase green density.

Niobium filaments, 250 μm in diameter were cut to a length of 5 mm to serve as the reinforcement. The surfaces were prepared for oxidation by first ultrasonically cleaning in acetone followed by an etch in a 1:2:3 solution of HF:HNO₃:H₂O and a final distilled water rinse. The filaments were then dried and placed in a quartz tube in a furnace at 500-525°C with a flowing oxygen atmosphere at 1 atm. pressure for approximately 6 minutes. As reported earlier¹³ the growth of Nb₂O₅ on the surface of the chopped filaments resulted in a continuous change of color, reflecting the oxide thickness.

The reactive sequences were inferred from differential thermal analysis (DTA) and microstructural evaluation performed at various stages during processing of the composites. The composites were tested for thermal stability by annealing in a gettered argon atmosphere at 1200°C for 100 hours. The fracture toughness of the composites was evaluated using three-point bending tests on chevron notched specimens (3.3 mm x 5 mm x greater than 2.5 mm) and four point bending tests on chevron notched specimens (3.8 mm x 5.1 mm x greater than 25 mm) with a test fixture span of 20 mm.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Development of Reactive Hot Compaction Cycles

The vacuum hot pressing cycles given in Figures 2.1 and 2.2 schematically show the control parameters developed to insure complete reaction of the powders, full development of the alumina interface and maximum densification of the composite. The temperatures, pressures and timing were developed to exploit the different reaction characteristics for each system. These reaction characteristics were determined from differential thermal analysis (Figures 3.1 and 3.2) and the microstructures of composites taken at various points during the processing of these composites as described below.

The DTA scan for NbAl₃ (Figure 3.1) shows an endothermic peak at 660°C, corresponding to the melting of the aluminum powder. This is followed by an exothermic peak starting at 870°C, centered at 980°C and ending at 1075°C, caused by the initiation of the self-propagating NbAl₃-formation reaction and its accompanying release of -119 kJ/mole heat of formation³. Thus, in the interval between 660°C and approximately 870°C aluminum exists as

a liquid phase. The liquid Al was forced into the gaps between Nb powder particles with the assistance of a small preload (10 MPa). This infiltration of a liquid phase into the powder compact aids densification by eliminating many inter-particle voids prior to the initiation of the intermetallic forming reaction. Also during this stage, an initial Al_2O_3 layer forms as the liquid Al comes in contact with the Nb_2O_5 surface of the reinforcement, as will be described in Section 3.2.

Above approximately 870°C , the intermetallic formation reaction was initiated. Use of large ($45\mu\text{m}$) Nb powders reveal a cored structure in incompletely reacted NbAl_3 matrices (Figure 3.3). A small Nb core is surrounded by an Nb_2Al intermetallic layer, which itself is surrounded by NbAl_3 intermetallic, indicating a two-step, diffusion controlled reaction sequence. Earlier work^{14,15} has concluded that during reactive synthesis, NbAl_3 is formed first, thus, the Nb_2Al must subsequently form by the outward diffusion of Nb from the core. The release of the heat of formation plus the externally supplied heat combine to accelerate the synthesis reaction. When the temperature reached 1350°C , the pressure was raised to 49 MPa. Holding at this temperature and pressure for one hour resulted in a homogenized microstructure with less than 2 percent porosity and completed the conversion of Nb_2O_5 to Al_2O_3 .

The time for the release of the ram pressure and the cooling rate after compaction were found to be critical for the prevention of cracks produced because of thermal expansion mismatch between the matrix and the reinforcement. When thermally induced stresses exceed the fracture stress of the matrix, small radial cracks appear in the matrix, emanating from the reinforcement/matrix interface. The cracking tendency increases as a function of the thermal expansion coefficient difference (mismatch), the diameter of the reinforcement and the cooling rate from the processing temperature. For the mismatch in NbAl_3/Nb composites in the present study, a cooling rate of $20^\circ\text{C}/\text{minute}$ was necessary to eliminate these cracks. It was also found that releasing the hot press ram pressure prior to the beginning of the cooling cycle aided in reducing mismatch-induced cracking.

The DTA curve for NiAl in Figure 3.2 shows only a very narrow reaction interval just above 600°C when the Ni and Al react to form NiAl for the processing sequence shown in Figure 2.2. A pressure of 50 MPa was applied at room temperature and maintained throughout the reaction and released just prior to the cool down cycle. For pure elemental powders as the starting species, the reaction occurs instantaneously, forming a solid network of NiAl containing large amounts of porosity. During the reaction it was observed that the hot press ram pressure would drop to zero, as the ram translated to partially compensate for the approximately 50 percent volume decrease upon the formation of solid NiAl. However, because of the rapid reaction rate, it was difficult to entirely eliminate the porosity. Similar to previous studies²⁰, it was found that the reaction could be slowed down by diluting the powder mixture with pre-reacted NiAl powder, other particulates and/or reinforcements. Figure 3.8 schematically shows the effect of dilution on reaction rate. A minimum dilution of 20 percent was found necessary to reduce the reaction rate such that the pressure can be maintained throughout the reaction by advancing the ram. It was found that the diluent particle size plays a major role in the retardation of the reaction. When diluent particles had the same size and up to three times the diameter as the elemental powders, the magnitude of the rate controlling effect is similar. When larger particles, approximately eight times the reacting powder diameters, were added a very slight effect was seen. And when the $250\mu\text{m}$ Nb diameter filaments (over 20 times the powder diameter) were added at 20 volume percent, no effect on the reaction rate could be detected. The further increase in temperature for these composites shown in Figure 2.2 is solely to facilitate the oxide conversion reaction necessary to form the interfacial diffusion barrier.

To prevent the thermally induced cracks of the compacts, the cooling rate from

the RHC temperature was found to be much more critical in NiAl-Nb composites, due to a much greater thermal expansion mismatch. In fact, for a cooling rate of less than 5°C/min., radial cracking occurred around 20% of the reinforcements with 250 μm diameter. For reinforcement diameters of 125 microns the incidence dropped to about 2%. No attempt was made to use finer reinforcements since it has been shown that the room temperature toughness in ductile fiber reinforced brittle matrices is a function of reinforcement diameter¹⁰ and for this system, 125 μm is close to the break-even point, where the toughening increase due to the load transfer to the reinforcement is offset by the decrease in toughness due to the increasing quantity of internal interfaces²¹. It is worth noting that recent work by the authors in micro-compositing the NiAl matrix with SiC whiskers and in-situ formed Al₂O₃ has been shown to produce composites without the incidence of radial cracks emanating from the reinforcement-matrix interface. This observation is explained on the basis of a reduced "effective thermal expansion" of the matrix by blending of thermal expansion characteristics of the NiAl matrix and the Al₂O₃ micro-reinforcement.

3.2 Niobium Reinforcements

Figures 3.5 and 3.6 show the extensive interactions between the matrix and the uncoated reinforcements in NbAl₃ and NiAl matrix composites, respectively, after fabrication. It can be seen that in the absence of an interfacial coating there is extensive filament/matrix interaction in the form of intermetallic formation as well as the penetration of aluminum (similar to grain boundary embrittlement) into the Nb filaments in NbAl₃ and ternary intermetallic formation in NiAl. Earlier work^{18,19,20} has shown that alumina can be used as a diffusion barrier coating on the reinforcement since it is stable in contact with both matrices and the reinforcement for at least 100 hours at 1200°C. They also found that the alumina coating could be developed in-situ, during RHC, by utilizing pre-oxidized niobium reinforcements. Figures 3.7 and 3.8 show the microstructure of two composites formed by this technique. The dark alumina interface is readily discernable in both micrographs, which show the absence of any detectable interaction between the matrices and the reinforcements in the composites after annealing at 1200°C for 100 hours. The sequence for the in-situ coating formation is that the surface oxide on the niobium filaments is reduced by the aluminum in the matrix to produce elemental Nb and Al₂O₃. Initially, a continuous layer of Al₂O₃ forms at the Nb₂O₅-matrix interface. The conversion of the remaining Nb₂O₅ to Al₂O₃ is accomplished via diffusion of Al from the matrix through the existing Al₂O₃ to the Al₂O₃-Nb₂O₅ interface. The rate of conversion seems to be controlled by a combination of the rate of Al transport across the Al₂O₃ and transport of the rejected Nb away from the interface.

Lu¹⁹ has shown that the final Al₂O₃ layer thickness is a linear function of the initial Nb₂O₅ layer thickness on the pretreated Nb filaments and obeys the relationship:

$$t_{Nb_2O_5} = 5.07 + 2.53t_{Al_2O_3}$$

where t_i is the thickness of the species i , in microns. He also has shown that the integrity and quality of the Al₂O₃ coating is strongly dependent on the quality and thickness of the Nb₂O₅ layer. For example, it was observed that when the Nb₂O₅ layer thickness exceeds approximately 20 microns, significant cracking of the oxide becomes apparent, due to the change in density from 8.4 g/cm³ for Nb to 4.7 g/cm³ for Nb₂O₅ (Pilling-Bedworth ratio=2.56). These cracks subsequently lead to the formation of non-uniform and incoherent Al₂O₃ coatings. A

discontinuous alumina coating provides short-circuit diffusion paths between the matrix and reinforcement and leads to extensive local matrix-reinforcement interaction.

Another source of cracks in the Nb_2O_5 surface layer is due to mechanical damage to the Nb filament during processing steps subsequent to the oxidation pretreatment. For chopped filaments this is most likely to occur during cold pressing the powder/filament blend. Replacing cold compaction with a gentle vibratory compaction for chopped filaments was found to minimize the rupture of the Nb_2O_5 surfaces. When continuous Nb filament reinforced composites are used, typically by a tape casting process, the Nb must be continuously oxidized, then taken up on a drum and covered with a binder to make a mat of continuous pretreated Nb filaments. The winding and unwinding of the oxidized filaments can cause cracking. Various diameter drums were evaluated for Nb_2O_5 thickness of approximately $9\ \mu\text{m}$ (the minimum thickness to produce an adequate Al_2O_3 layer). It was found that below 5 cm diameter, fissures appeared in the tensile edge of the Nb_2O_5 layer (away from the surface of the drum). The number of fissures increased with decreasing radius of curvature. Thus the oxidized niobium does have some damage tolerance if proper precautions are taken.

3.3 Fracture Toughness of NbAl_3 -Nb Composites

Three-point bend tests on chevron-notched samples were utilized to evaluate the fracture toughness of the monolithic matrix and composites with in-situ coated niobium filaments. Figure 3.9 compares the load-displacement curves for NbAl_3 and the Nb/ NbAl_3 composite. The fracture of unreinforced matrix material shows typical catastrophic brittle behavior. The composite, alternately, shows an initial linear elastic region, followed by a non-linear load increase with some smaller perturbations up to the maximum load followed by a stepwise load decrease. The higher peak load and damage tolerance both indicate an effective transfer of load to the reinforcement.

The fracture surface for the unreinforced NbAl_3 , with intergranular and intermittent transgranular cleavage features, is shown in Figure 3.10. In comparison, the fracture surface of the composite, shown in Figure 3.11 indicates partial decohesion of the filaments and their ductile failure. The figure demonstrates the significant degree of debonding and bridging by the niobium reinforcements. Closer examination of the fracture topography reveals that crack deflection occurred near the niobium filaments, indicating the existence of a residual stress field in the vicinity of the reinforcement-matrix interface.

The toughening behavior of a ductile reinforcement in a brittle matrix has been linked to the degree of debonding at the interface²⁴⁻²⁶. For the present composites, the elastic modulus of the matrix is greater than the elastic modulus of the reinforcement. Thus, at low strains, a disproportionately high fraction of the load is carried by the matrix, resulting in premature failure of the brittle matrix and transfer of the load to the reinforcement in the crack wake^{27,28}. The degree of debonding at the interface defines a gage length for the bridging reinforcements in the crack wake. This length of the reinforcements is unconstrained and deforms in a ductile manner, while the proportion of the reinforcement remaining bonded at the interface serves to couple the load to the reinforcement. Thus an intermediate level of interfacial debonding is desired to provide an optimum toughening of the brittle matrix with ductile reinforcements.

The evidence in the fracture surface of the NbAl_3 -Nb composite suggests a fairly optimal degree of interfacial debonding at the Al_2O_3 -Nb interface. The ductile failure of the reinforcements as suggested by the high degree of necking and microvoid coalescence, the length of filament pull-out, together with the stepwise load drop indicate effective load transfer just

before or during matrix failure. If this were not the case, an abrupt drop in the load would occur as the crack reached the critical size in the brittle matrix, or, in the other extreme, the Nb would have failed in a more brittle manner, due to constraint at the interface. Thus, the in-situ formed alumina interface possesses a nearly optimum balance of strength; weak enough to allow partial decohesion, but strong enough to provide for effective load transfer.

3.4 Conclusions

By coupling the RHC process with oxidation pre-treatment of niobium filaments, aluminide matrix composites were produced with a diffusion barrier coating formed in-situ at the reinforcement-matrix interface. Somewhat different processing routes were necessitated by the reaction kinetics inherent to the two systems. Nb/NbAl₃ composites were formed via transient liquid phase sintering, followed by more traditional sintering to full density, whereas Nb/NiAl composites were produced by dynamic reactive sintering, which is characterized by obtaining densification by controlling the reaction rate. Post-annealing microstructures revealed that the Al₂O₃ layer formed in-situ acts as an effective diffusion barrier in both systems and eliminates the extensive interaction between matrix and reinforcement seen in the untreated specimens. The fracture toughness was substantially improved in the Nb/NbAl₃ composites, whereas thermal expansion mismatch-induced cracking precluded meaningful fracture toughness testing of the NiAl matrix composites. Fracture surface features indicate partial decohesion of the Al₂O₃-matrix interface occurs during crack propagation. Thus the in-situ coating provides both an excellent diffusion barrier and a balance of strength to facilitate various toughening and strengthening mechanisms.

Acknowledgement

The authors gratefully acknowledge the support of Defense Advanced Research Projects Agency through ONR Grant #N00014-91-J-4075.

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Figure 2.1. Schematic RHC processing cycle for Nb-NbAl₃ composites²¹

Figure 2.2. Schematic RHC processing cycle for Nb-NiAl composites

Figure 3.1. Differential thermal analysis scan for reactively produced NbAl₃²¹.

Figure 3.2. Differential thermal analysis scan for reactively produced NiAl.

Figure 3.3. Incompletely reacted NbAl_3 matrix, illustrating the cored structure due to large Nb powders. Large particles contain Nb-rich cores indicated by arrows²¹.

Figure 3.4. Schematic showing the effect of dilution with prealloyed NiAl powder on the relative reaction rate.

Figure 3.5. Micrograph showing extensive interaction between the NbAl_3 matrix and Nb reinforcement for untreated filaments (as hot pressed)²¹. (Polarized light)

Figure 3.6. Micrograph showing extensive interaction between the NiAl matrix and Nb reinforcement for untreated filaments (as hot pressed). (Marble's reagent)

Figure 3.7. Micrograph showing the effectiveness of the in-situ Al_2O_3 diffusion barrier coating after 100 hr at 1200°C in NbAl_3^{21} . (Polarized light)

Figure 3.8. Micrograph showing the effectiveness of the in-situ Al_2O_3 diffusion barrier coating after 100 hr at 1200°C in NiAl . (Marble's reagent)

Figure 3.9. Load-Displacement curves for unreinforced and Nb/In-situ coated NbAl₃²¹.

Figure 3.10. NbAl₃ fracture surface.

Figure 3.11. NbAl₃-Nb composite fracture surface, showing detail of filament pull-out and ductile fracture of Nb filaments²¹.